

ISic0110

I.Sicily inscription 0110

Language

Latin

Type

building

Material

limestone

Object

block

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico Baldassare Romano

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 32 cm

Width 63 cm

Depth 33 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]aedific[---]

2. [---] Viviañi potes[---]

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284842

EDR 110891

EDCS 10900638

Bibliography

Bivona, L. 1994. *Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese. Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica*. Palermo / Rome. At 28

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 480-481 no.21
Henzen, W., Zangemeister, K. F. W. 1872-1913. *Ephemeris epigraphica. Corporis
inscriptionum Latinarum supplementum*, edita iussu Instituti archaeologici
Romani. Berlin. At VIII 698

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0110. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI
edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4334166>